

SAICHEN: CONFLICT WITHOUT END

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ABSTRACT

The connection between India Pakistan plummeted to its lowest levels in the late 1980s as the militancy was stepped up in Kashmir by Pakistan. This is not to agree that there have been patches of collaboration when peace efforts were made, particularly during the leadership of Rajiv Gandhi and Benazir Bhutto in observe to the Siachen, conflict. However, in general, the connection has been hostile and bitter. After the murder of Rajiv Gandhi and overthrow of Benazir, peace efforts were struggling to take off until I. K. Gujaral and Nawaz Sharif took charge. Hopes were raised on mutually sides of the border that the two prime ministers, being Punjabis, would welcome each other improved. Both took initiatives to resume the delayed talks and showed their decide to remove the barriers from Indo-Pakistani ties. In India, headship changed hands normally from the mid 1990s onwards. Pakistan was a bit stable under Nawaz Sharif who had shown the interest in humanizing relations with India. But with the coming one of the Bhartiya Janata Party to power In India, doubts were bound to be expressed in Pakistan. Though Atal Behari Vajpayee lasted only 11 days as Prime Minister, his next tenure in 1998 proved otherwise. This time, leading a alliance government, Vajpayee was solid in proving his critics, both in India and Pakistan, wrong by making honest efforts to improve the connection. Vajpayee tried to work out his family and external agendas in tandem. On the one hand in May 1998, he gave consent to check five nuclear devices in Pokhran and step up the missile programme, and on the other, he comprehensive his hand of familiarity to Pakistan. In return, Pakistan responded by explosion its first ever nuclear machine in the Chagai hills and carrying out a succession of missile tests. Amidst these developments Vajpayee also made a momentous bus trip to Lahore through the Wagah border and signed the Lahore statement there with Nawaz Sharif.

Keywords: Clash, missile tests, siachen, Battle

THE SIACHEN CONFLICT

The highest battlefield in the global, the Siachen Glacier has witnessed conflict between India and Pakistan for fourteen years. It has so far resulted in hundreds of casualties caused mostly by adverse climatic conditions and harsh terrain rather than military skirmishes. The conflict is also putting an enormous financial burden on the national exchequer on both sides. Siding down a valley in the Karakoram Range, the glacier is 76 kilometers long and varies in

width between 2 to 8 kilometers. It receives up to 6 to 7 meters of the annual total of 10 meters of snow in the winter months. Blizzards can reach speeds of up to 150 knots (nearly 300 kilometers per hour). The temperature drops routinely to 40 degrees centigrade below zero, and even lower with the wind chill factor. For these reasons the Siachen glacier has been called the "Third Pole" [1]

The altitude of some Indian forward bases on the Salto Ridge range from Kumar

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(16,000 feet) and Bila Top (18,600 feet) to Pahalwan (20,000 feet) and Indira Col (22,000 feet). Because of the steep gradient of the Salto Range, the area is also prone to avalanches. These adverse conditions have direct consequences: since the war began, only 3 percent of the Indian casualties have been caused by hostile firing. The remaining 97 percent have fallen prey to the altitude, weather, and terrain [2].

Pakistani combat casualties are low because troops of dug in, artillery fire over mountain peaks is generally inaccurate, and infantry assaults are seldom made in the harsh climate and difficult terrain. Most Pakistani casualties, too, occur because of the climate, terrain, and altitude. Pakistani positions are, for the most part, at a lower altitude in the glacier area, ranging between 9,000 to 15,000 feet (some are at a much higher altitude such as Conway Saddle, at 17,200 feet, which controls ingress to the glacier).

A History of the Siachen Conflict

The State of Jammu and Kashmir had formally and legally acceded to India in accordance with the provisions of the Transfer of Power Act passed by the British Parliament which granted British India its independence. The instrument of accession of the State was duly accepted by the British Governor General of India on October 26, 1947, on the recommendation of the Government of India. That the whole State of Jammu and Kashmir is an integral part of India from the date on is therefore unquestionable in the Indian view. On the other hand Pakistan until now has maintained a fairly ambiguous position in respect of its jurisdiction over different parts of the State occupied by it in 1947-48. As a consequence, Azad ("Independent") Kashmir does not appear on any published Pakistani map, and it has its own constitution, its own capital city (Muzafarabad), a full-fledged Government, a national flag, but without a formal recognition by Pakistan. Zulfikar Ali Bhutto's effort to integrate Azad Kashmir into Pakistan as a fifth state in 1973 was strenuously objected to by Kashmir constitution to include provisions

granting the area its own Supreme Court, Prime Minister, and Chief Election Commissioner, thus reinforcing the political separateness of Azad Kashmir from Pakistan. Pakistan has maintained a different position with regard to the Northern Areas (of J&K State) which Bhutto insisted did not belong to the between Azad Kashmir and the Northern Areas (which include the erstwhile principalities in the state of Jammu and Kashmir). For instance, General Zia-ul-Haq maintained a contradictory stand. He was quoted as having said that the Northern Areas including Baltistan, were disputed areas but part of Pakistan [3]. Two years later, he was reported to have stated that the Siachen Glaciers lay in disputed territory and that it was a no man's land [4].

The reason for the controversy is that the Siachen Glacier region falls within the undelineated territory beyond the last defined section of the LOC map grid (point NJ 9842). As a result Indian and Pakistanis have tried to stake their territorial claims by interpreting the vague language contained in the 1949 and 1972 agreements to prove their respective points. For Pakistan thence northwards" means from NJ 9842 up to the Karakoram Pass [5]. India, on the other hand draws a north westerly line from NJ 9742 along the watershed line of the Salto Range, a southern offshoot of the Karakoram Range [6].

Military Confrontation on the Siachen Glacier

Who has done an in depth study of the Siachen writers: What is publicly known about events leading upto the outbreak of hostilities in the vicinity of the Siachen Glacier in the winter of 1983-84 does not supply unambiguous evidence who shot first is probably impossible to determine. Which of since the question of the legitimacy of the two sides" territorial claims have never been submitted to impartial adjudication is a matter obviously open to disagreement. There is ample evidence, however, that the Indian armed forces were the first to establish permanent posts on the glacier and that they had prepared themselves long and well for the task. Published Indian accounts of

operation Meghdoot leave little room for doubt, in fact, that the Pakistanis were caught napping and that their principal strategy for fortifying Pakistan's claim to the glacier sponsoring foreign mountaineering expeditions to the area had failed [7].

General Chiber, justifying the logic of operation Meghdoot in 1984, refers to his 1978 decision to sanction the first Indian expedition to Siachen, colonel N. Kumar's "Operational patrol" to Teram Kangri in the Siachen area. The discussion was influenced, he recalls by an episode in the mid-1950s, when the Government of India had turned down the Army's plans for of Kashmir only to discover one to the Aksai Chin area northeast of Kashmir only to discover one day that that the Chinese had built 1978, it was decided that the Siachen area "should be regularly patrolled during the summer months" but that" it would be impractical to establish a post in such a hostile environment" [8]. Although Pakistan claims that twenty mountaineering expeditions were undertaken between 1974 and 1980 (mainly by Europeans and Japanese), Chibber makes the claim that nonse came thereafter [9].

Siachen's Significance for India

From an Indian perspective, the Siachen Glacier is the wedge of territory that separates Pakistan-occupied Kashmir (POK) from Aksai Chin, the part of Kashmir claimed and occupied by China [10]. In Indian perceptions Siachen's geostrategic importance lies in the fact that its control would support the defence of Ladakh, Jammu and Kashmir against Pakistan and /or Chinese threats [11]. It would prevent the outflanking of Indian forces in the Leh and Kargil sectors and the outflanking of Indian forces in the Leh and Kargil sectors and the connecting of the Aksai Chin highway with the Karakoram pass. Control over Siachen would enable India to keep watch over the Karakoram highway and the Khunjarab pass, while fortifying India's position in border negotiations with China [12].

For India controlling the commanding heights is a crucial aspect of the Siachen conflict. This issue flows out of basic infantry

tactics: height confers a tactical advantage. According to General Chibber, the notion that "reasonably well-prepared defensive positions. He argues that "at these formidable altitudes it is difficult almost impossible to dislodge a force that occupies a height" [13].

But India has disadvantages too. As long as Pakistan does not commit its forces to an offensive against the Indian positions, the Indians have the disadvantage of being deployed at much higher attitudes. In order to block Pakistan's access to the Siachen Glacier India has no option but to maintain its hazardous post on the Saltoro Ridge, thereby exposing its forces to the dangerous altitude, weather, and terrain. India's strategy is also extremely expensive in financial terms and most of the Indian pickets and posts on the Saltoro Ridge are air maintained. Personnel, weapons and ammunition, fuel and food are usually flown in by helicopters and occasionally paraded. As M.J. Akbar remarks, "India's problems are greater than Pakistan's because the latter's supply lines need road; our need helicopters"

India's Stand on Siachen

India has interpreted thence northwards to the glaciers" to mean that the LOC proceeds from NJ 9842 along with watershed line that Saltoro range. Air Commodore Jasjit Singh says that "in mountainous terrain the high crest line marking the watershed is the internationally accepted norm for working out boundary settlements, much as the Thalweg (or themed-channel) riverine principle is used to delicate boundaries along rivers" [14]. However, India's declared policy is not a sufficient indicator of the different perspectives, concerns, and objectives in the Indian policy community on the Siachen dispute. According to Samina Ahmed and Varun Sahni, three alternatives are readily discernible in India: (1) maintaining the deployment on Siachen at all costs, (2) negotiating a military disengagement with Pakistan, and (3) withdrawing Indian forces from the Glaciers unilaterally if necessary [15].

A. G. Noorani thinks that a negotiated or unilateral Indian withdrawal would be a wise decision as the disputed region is uninhabitable

and has no strategic value. Some believe that a Siachen settlement could be the first step in the resolution of the Kashmir dispute [16]. Lt. Gen. Massih whose brigade was posted in Siachen for one year remarks. "Siachen is a political problem and not a military one. If guys in Delhi decide to pull out from Saltoro ridge the army would have no problems in that" [17]. But J.N. Dixit, former Indian Foreign secretary strongly reacts to Massih's remarks saying, "There's a great deal of ambiguity on the part of the military. Why does the military not go and say that Siachen does not have any strategic significance. Calling it just a political problem is nonsense. Of course, all problems are political first" [18].

.Pakistan's Stand on Siachen

Pakistan's official stand for always been averse to India's presence on the Glacier and always questioned India's right to be there. The Siachen Glacier and its approaches are located within Baltistan in the Pakistan administered northern territories. Pakistan will not accept the status quo on Siachen because India's military presence on the glacier and environs, in its view, is illegal and unlawful. Pakistani policy makers rule out any unilateral withdrawal and seem to have the following policy options: (1) to continue the armed conflict, (2) to sign an agreement limited to conflict containment; or (3) to reach a comprehensive and permanent settlement with India. The adoption of any of these options depends on the perceptions, preferences, and bargaining power of various sections of Pakistan's policy-making community [19].

Hardliners within the Pakistan military and bureaucracy favour the continuation of conflict because India is perceived as the aggressor. Major General Jehangir Nasrullah, head of Pakistan's armed forces' Inter-Service Public Relations, declared, "Every square inch is sovereign territory. You can't throw it away [20].

The segment with a moderate view favour's a negotiated settlement. Announcing the resolve of the Nawaz Sharif government to maintain, normal good neighbourly relations

with India," Foreign office spokesman Khalid Saleem declared that, "we are always willing to discuss the question of withdrawing troops from Siachen provided it is based on agreements and agreed principles" [21]. For this segment holding on a Siachen does not make any sense as the Pakistani casualties and the economic burden do not justify sustaining a conflict over inhospitable territory with no population or resource and little geostrategic territory with no population or resources and little geostrategic value [22]. Even among Pakistani supporters of a negotiated settlement, however, there are concerns based on a history of mistrust that India would attempt to use a settlement to legitimize its claim over the disputed area. Pakistan has rejected any Indian presence in the area. According to the Minister of State for Defence Rana Naeem Mahmood, in the first rounds of negotiations in 1986 and 1987, Pakistan had rejected Indian demands for a withdrawal to pre-1984 positions must precede any agreement stand called for the withdrawal of troops to positions held at the time the 1972 Simla Agreement, when the line of the control was demarcated [23].

Negotiations on the Siachen Conflict

For the first time, in 1984, the Siachen glacier boundary issue was added to the list of major issues of contention between the two countries. In December 1985 Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi and President Zai-ul-Haq agreed in New Delhi to hold talks at the Defence Secretaries level on the Siachen issue. During the first round of Defense Secretaries' talks in January 1986, both sides indulged in accusing the other of violating the Simla Agreement. Furthermore Pakistan cited the statements of India Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru and India's protests in 1962-63 over Sino-Pakistani negotiations, which resulted in the boundary agreement of 1963, and from these. It attempted to infer India's recognition of Pakistan's possession of areas to the west of the Karakoram Pass. Specifically, Pakistan cited India's protest note of May 10, 1962, which referred to "that portion of the boundary between India and China west of the Karakoram Pass which is presently under Pakistani's unlawful

occupation” [24]. It also cited Nehru’s statement in Parliament on March 5, 1963 which said that “Pakistan’s Line of actual control. Reached the Karakoram Pass [25].

The second round of talks in June 1986 saw a repeat of familiar assertions on both sides. India hinted at a cease-fire in all but name and proposed an accord on non-escalation of the situation. Pakistan rejected anything approximating a cease-fire. The talks were reportedly held in a “cordial and friendly atmosphere” and it was agreed that the talks should be continued at a later date. There was no signs of any material progress, however. The talks were highly repetitious, a “pantomime” of the first [26].

The fourth round of talks were scheduled to be held in New Delhi in September 1988 in a new political atmosphere because of the death of Zia-ul-Haq in August in a plane crash. The interim government announced that it would hold elections in the coming November to choose a new leader this time a civilian. Pakistan, despite these surprising political developments, wanted to carry on the process of dialogues.

On February 8, 1989, Prime Minister Benazir Bhutto had expected India to withdraw its forces to the 1972 pre-Simla positions [27].

Pakistan’s formal terms by the opening of the fifth round of talks, by contrast, were fewer in number. As identified for A. G. Noorani by members of the Pakistani delegation to the fifth round, they contained two essential points:

1. Deployment of Indian and Pakistani forces to mutually agreed positions held at the time the ceasefire was declared in 1971 (ie., pre-Simla positions); and only then.
2. Delimitation of an extension of the LOC beyond map reference point NJ 984246.

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